

ATTITUDES TOWARD SCHOOLING AND PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES: EFFECT ON THE SOCIAL-EMOTIONAL LEARNING ADJUSTMENT AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the association between attitudes towards schooling, parental exposure to different kinds of parent and school engagement activities and demonstrated the degree of relationship and positive link between parental involvement and attitudes toward to social emotional learning adjustment academic performance of the students. The study employed descriptive - correlational method of research to conduct the study to the 95 parents and 95 Grade 8 students in the Silangang Malicboy National High School, Pagbilao District II of Division of Quezon. Three different data collection tools were used: survey questionnaire and academic performance of students for 1st and 2nd quarter Data were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Five (5) key findings from this research are: 1) It revealed that both parent and student respondents generally perceived the level of attitude towards schooling demonstrated strongly agree and with high positive attitude towards schooling. 2) The parent – respondents have very highly involved/very highly engaged in communicating and learning at home. Meanwhile, the student – respondent perceived the level of parental engagement strategies of their parents as very highly involved/very highly engage in communicating and decision making. 3). The student – respondents have very highly adjustment in relationship skills while the other social emotional learning related variables likewise social knowledge, self – management, self – awareness and decision making skills have high adjustment. 4) In determining the test of relationship, all related variables of attitudes toward schooling and parental engagement strategies have the positive relationship to student’s academic performance. Meanwhile, the parental engagement strategies related variables have positive relationship and build connections to the social emotional learning adjustments 5) Results indicated that this study has demonstrated that the Guidance and Counselling Program may be relevant to the parenting skills, boosting parent and child relationship and developing decision making skills of adolescence may be designed to enhance the student’s academic performance in this new normal schooling.

Keywords: Attitudes, Enhanced Guidance Program, Parental Engagement strategies, Social-emotional Learning Adjustment, Parents, Students